

Determinants of Emotional Intelligence of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated determinants of emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted. Population of the study 16,660 senior secondary school students in all the 16 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. Sample size of the study was 391 respondents which was determined using Taro Yamene's formula. Simple random sampling technique was for the sample selection. An instrument titled: "Questionnaire on Determinants of Students' Emotional Intelligence" (QDSEI) was used for data collection. The Simple Regression Analysis was used to answer the research questions and also test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that: Home environment, locus of control and psychological wellbeing significantly predicted emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. Recommendations were made that: Parents should make the home environment to be conducive as to enhance the emotional intelligence of the students, and that students should develop internal locus of control in order to believe in themselves, as well as improve their emotional intelligence for better performance in school.

Keywords: Determinant, emotional intelligence, home environment, locus of control psychological wellbeing

INTRODUCTION

In every community or society at large, healthy human relationship is necessary for peaceful co-existence between and among people. However, in order to achieve healthy human relationship, individuals need to utilize their emotional intelligence. Emotional Intelligence can be defined as the intellectual ability and skill to regulate emotion, develop self-control, resolve conflict and exercise good leadership in any given setting. Emotional intelligence can manage emotions fruitfully during stressful situations. Emotional intelligence is the component of competencies, talents, and skills of an individual which comprises a body of knowledge required to deal with life effectively in different day to day situations (Saikia & Borah, 2022). Emotional Intelligence is the intellectual ability and skill to regulate emotion, develop self-control, resolve conflict and exercise good leadership in any given setting. Emotional intelligence can also be viewed as the ability to quick and control emotions that make peoples more intelligent (Robinson, Hull & Petrides, 2020).

Emotional intelligence has two types of competencies – personal and social competencies. Personal competencies include major factors namely; self-awareness, self-regulation, self-control, self-motivation, self-consciousness, empathy and social skills. The five dimensions of emotional intelligence as discussed below are self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and relationship management (Goleman as cited in Ugoani, Amu & Kalu, 2015).

- a. Self-awareness: Self-awareness occurs when the individual knows what he is feeling in the moment, and using those preferences to guide decision making, having a realistic assessment of his own abilities and a well-grounded sense of self-confidence.

- b. Self-regulation: This involves handling our emotions so that they facilitate rather than interfere with the task at hand; having conscientious and delaying gratification, to pursue goals; recovering well from emotional distress.
- c. Motivation: This dimension of emotional intelligence involves using available deepest preferences to move and guide the individual toward desired goals, to help in taking initiative and striving. To improve, and to persevere in the face of setbacks and frustration.
- d. Empathy: This is related to sensing what other people are feeling, being able to take their perspective, and cultivating rapport and attunement with a broad diversity of people.
- e. Relationship management: Relationship management manifests in handling emotions in relationships well and accurately reading social situations and networks, interacting smoothly; using these skills to persuade and lead, negotiate and settle disputes, for cooperation and teamwork (Goleman as cited in Ugoani, Amu & Kalu, 2015).

Different factors such as family, school, religion, peer pressure, learning style, locus of control among others could determine the emotional intelligence of students, but the focus of this study is on home environment, locus of control and psychological wellbeing as determinants of emotional intelligence of secondary school students. Home environment is the first point of interaction and learning after birth in which the parents' attitude, actions and other characteristics help to shape the growth and development of a child. This implies that the nature of home environment could have significant influence on the overall development of a child because his/ her socialization and learning processes begins and continue after school hours. At home, the child learns and develops his thinking capacity and acquires the values of the society which can shape his/ her personality.

Naik and Shukla (2018) investigated on impact on home environment on social and emotional intelligence of adolescents and found that there is a significant impact of home environment on interactional effect of social and emotional intelligence of both boys and girls" student of higher secondary schools. Kumar (2020) observed that emotional intelligence was independent of gender, subject, locality of the school, type of family, fathers' occupation and family income, and that the female students possess better emotional intelligence than the male students. Contrarily, Singh and Sagar (2019) conducted a study on emotional intelligence and home environment of senior secondary students and their findings showed that there is no significant interaction effect between home environment and gender on emotional intelligence of senior secondary students.

Locus of control is a trait that relates to one's perception of events in his life or one's responsibility for what happens to him or her. Locus of control is known as the most important axis of personality which is classified as internal and external. Individuals who believe that they have no control over events in their lives have an external locus of control (Variya & Jigar, 2023), while those who believe that they have control over events that happens in their life have an internal locus of control. Variya and Jigar (2023) explained that the first systematic study of locus of control was initiated by Rotter in 1966 which gave a new direction to the study of various aspects of personality, psycho-physiological processes and the field of psychology. Shah (2017) examined emotional intelligence among adolescents in relation to their test anxiety and academic stress and found a significance difference among gender in relation to emotional intelligence and test anxiety. Also, in their study on Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity in Young Male and Female, Dudhatra and Jogsan (2017) revealed that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and social maturity in young males and females

Psychological wellbeing of a student is another important factor that deserves research attention especially in relation to emotional intelligence of the student. The concept of wellbeing is seemingly complex in its definition because it encompasses a holistic perspective of individual wellness (Schoeman, 2012), which seem to have made the debate over what constitute an individual's 'wellbeing' to take different perspectives in research. However, Salami (2010) defined psychological wellbeing is as a state that emerges from feeling of satisfaction with one's physical health and oneself as a person and with one's close interpersonal relationships. Nondumiso (2017) described

psychological wellbeing as the overall effectiveness of a person's psychological functioning. Deci and Ryan (2008) observed that majority of researchers employ two common approaches in defining wellbeing, which according to them are hedonia (subjective wellbeing) and eudaimonia (psychological wellbeing). The subjective wellbeing refers to the people's evaluation of their own lives including cognitive judgements and emotional responses (Tripathi, 2011).

Deci and Ryan (2008) suggested that psychological wellbeing and subjective wellbeing should be viewed as one in order to obtain optimal wellbeing of an individual. This could be because psychological wellbeing encompasses the overall effectiveness of a person's psychological functioning (Nondumiso, 2017). Mehmood and Gulzar (2014) revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and self-esteem, and a negative association between emotional intelligence and depression. Ruiz-Aranda, Extremera and Pineda-Galán (2014) who investigated emotional intelligence, life satisfaction and subjective happiness in female student health professionals: the mediating effect of perceived stress in a 12-week follow-up study observed that participants with higher emotional intelligence recorded less perceived stress and higher levels of life satisfaction and happiness, which implies that perceived stress mediates the relationship between emotional intelligence and well-being indicators, such as life satisfaction and happiness. In the same vein, Mehmood and Gulzar (2014) examined the connection of emotional intelligence with adolescent's psychological wellbeing (depression and self-esteem) and revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and self-esteem, and a negative association between emotional intelligence and depression.

This study was anchored on the Rational Emotive Behaviour Theory by Albert Ellis (1950). The Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT) was introduced by Albert Ellis as an approach that for identifying irrational beliefs and negative thought patterns that may lead to emotional or behavioural issues. Albert Ellis argued that though people exhibit both rational and irrational behaviour, irrational thinking occurs in early illogical learning as a result of continuous emotional disturbance such as anxiety, depression, hatred, guilt among others. According to the theory, though some illogical thinking in people can attributed to biological limitations, most of them are shaped through socialization processes that are done through parents, teachers, peer groups, mass media and society. The irrational or irrational beliefs of an individual can be explained in four basic principles known as the A-B-C-D principles to enhance proper understanding of the causality between thoughts and emotions. In this regard, Ellis argued by focusing on the philosophic reconstruction of the life style of a person, therapist can devices techniques to make people with maladaptive behaviour to get better and feels better about themselves. Based on these assumptions, Ellis introduced the reconstruction into the principle to become A-B-C-D-E. A is the Activating Factor, B is the Belief or Self thought, C is the Consequences of self-thought, D is the Disputation and E is the Re-education (E).

In their own experiment, Wood, Barker, Turner and Sheffield (2018) noted that the therapy was able to control the irrational thinking of adolescent students with maladaptive behaviours using the ABC part of the principle, and thus explained that the A which is the Activating Factor is the maladaptive behaviour situation of the person, B which is the Belief refers to the situation where by the adjusted person begins to blame himself with different irrational thinking such as: "I am finished", "everybody is running away from me", "nobody wants to interact with me". But at the C, these irrational thoughts result in isolation, self-denial, hatred for life. The theory is very relevant to this study because the ABC part of the principle can be used to improve the students' locus of control and emotional intelligence in any environment for their wellbeing.

Statement of the Problem

Emotional intelligence is important in the life of every individual. It is the component of competencies, talents, and skills of an individual which comprises a body of knowledge required to deal with life effectively in different day to day situations. Many studies have shown the link between emotional intelligence of adolescents in secondary schools and some family characteristics. For instance, Kumar (2020) revealed that emotional intelligence was independent of gender, type of

family, fathers' occupation and family income. Naik and Shukla (2018) also found that there is a significant impact of home environment on interactional effect of social and emotional intelligence of both boy and girl students of higher secondary schools. However, there seem to be paucity of empirical studies in recent times that combined emotional intelligence, locus of control, psychological wellbeing and home environment secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, and this gap motivated the researcher to go into this present study. Hence, the study investigated the determinants of emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State with focus on the home environment, locus of control and psychological wellbeing of students.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate factors that predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which home environment predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.
2. Examine the extent to which locus of control predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.
3. Examine the extent to which psychological well-being predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does home environment predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area?
2. To what extent does locus of control predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area?
3. To what extent does psychological well-being predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. Home environment does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.
2. Locus of control does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.
3. Psychological wellbeing does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

RESEARCH METHOD

The correlational research design was adopted. Onunkwo as cited in Ogidi (2018) defined correlational research design as the research design that is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables as well as the direction and magnitude of such relationship. The correlational research design was chosen for the study because it enables the researcher to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The population of the study was 16,660 senior secondary school students in all the 16 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. The population of the study was made up of 8,545 male and 8,115 female students (Source: Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, Port Harcourt, 2024). The sample of this study was 391 SSS 2 students in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area made up of 195

male and 196 female students. Taro Yamane’s formula was used to determine the sample size of the study.

Simple random sampling technique was used to select 8 public senior secondary schools for the study. The simple random sampling technique was also used to select 195 male students and 196 female students from the 8 randomly chosen schools out of 16 schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area for the study. An instrument titled: “Questionnaire on Determinants of Students’ Emotional Intelligence” (QDSEI) was used for data collection. The QDSEI was used to elicit information on home environment, locus of control, psychological well-being and emotional intelligence of students with 4 items for each; hence the instrument was made up of 16 items in all prepared on a four-point response scale ranging from Very High Extent (VHE) with weighted 4 points to Very Low Extent (VLE) with weighted 1 point respectively.

The face and content validity of the instrument was determined by two experts in Counselling Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The experts reviewed the instrument in terms of the items clarity, suitability of the words, content coverage, adequacy and relevance in addressing the purpose of the study and research questions, and made corrections which formed the basis for the final print out of the instrument. The Cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the reliability coefficients of the instrument with 30 selected public senior secondary students in a school that was not part of the sampled schools and it yielded 0.72, 0.76, 0.73 and 0.75 reliability coefficients for home environment, locus of control, psychological well-being and emotional intelligence clusters respectively. The Simple Regression Analysis was used to answer the research questions and also test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: To what extent does home environment predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area?

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent Home Environment Predicts Emotional Intelligence of Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.189 ^a	.636	.634	2.72842

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Home environment
- b. Dependent Variable: emotional intelligence of students

Table 1 presents the simple regression analysis on the extent to home environment predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. From the results in Table 1, it can be observed that $R = 0.189^a$, $R\text{ Square} = 0.636$ and $\text{Adjusted } R\text{ Square} = 0.634$. The high value of Adjusted R Square (0.634) indicated that home environment predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area to a high extent. This result revealed that home environment accounted for 63.4% of the total variance observed in the prediction of emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, while the remaining 36.6% could be due to other factors that are not considered in the study.

Research Question 2: To what extent does locus of control predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area?

Table 4.2: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent Locus Of Control Predict emotional Intelligence of Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.116 ^a	.213	.442	2.76031

a. Predictors: (Constant), Locus of control

b. Dependent Variable: Emotional intelligence of students

From the data in Table 2, it can be observed that the R-value = 0.116^a, R Square = 0.213 and Adjusted R Square = 0.442. The Adjusted R Square of 0.442 implies that locus of control predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area to a moderate extent. Adjusted R Square (0.442) further showed that locus of control accounted for 44.2% (0.442 x 100) of the variance observed in the prediction of emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students while the remaining 55.8% could be due to other factors that are not considered in the study.

Research Question 3: To what extent does psychological wellbeing predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area?

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent Psychological Wellbeing Predict Emotional Intelligence of Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.180 ^a	.632	.631	2.73276

a. Predictors: (Constant), Psychological wellbeing

b. Dependent Variable: Emotional intelligence of students

Table 3 presents the simple regression analysis of the extent to which psychological wellbeing predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. The data in Table 3 indicated that R = 0.180^a, R-Square = 0.632 and Adjusted R Square = 0.631. The high value of R-Adj² (0.631) indicates that psychological wellbeing predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area to a high extent, with the prediction accounting for 63.1% (R-Adj² = 0.631) of the total variance and residuals observed in emotional intelligence of students, while the remaining 36.9% could be due to other factors and residuals that are not considered in the study.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Home environment does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Table 4: Regression ANOVA on Prediction of Home Environment to Emotional Intelligence of Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	205.785	1	205.785	27.643	.000 ^b	Ho Rejected
	Residual	5568.323	384	7.444			
	Total	5774.108	385				

a. Dependent Variable: Emotional intelligence of students

b. Predictors: (Constant), Home environment

Data in Table 4 reveals that F-value = 27.643, p-value = 0.000^b and degrees of freedom (df) = 1 and 384. Since $F_{(1, 384)} = 27.643$ and p-value (0.000) < 0.05, the null hypothesis which states that home environment does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area was therefore rejected. Hence, it was concluded that home

environment significantly predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. This implies that home environment is a strong determinant of students' emotional intelligence.

Hypothesis 2: Locus of control does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Table 5: Regression ANOVA on Prediction of Locus of Control to Emotional Intelligence of Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	74.879	1	74.879	9.828	.002 ^b	Ho Rejected
	Residual	5699.229	384	7.619			
	Total	5774.108	385				

a. Dependent Variable: Emotional intelligence of students

b. Predictors: (Constant), Locus of control

Table 5 presents the Regression ANOVA on significant prediction of locus of control to emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. The results in Table 5 revealed that F-value = 9.828, p-value = 0.002^b and degrees of freedom (df) = 1 and 384. Since $F_{(1, 384)} = 9.828$ and p-value (0.002) < 0.05. Since the p-value (0.002) < 0.05, the null hypothesis which states that locus of control does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area was therefore rejected and the alternative accepted. Thus, it was concluded that locus of control significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area ($F_{(1, 384)} = 9.828$; $p < 0.05$). The implication of this result is that locus of control is a contributor of emotional intelligence of students.

Hypothesis 3: Psychological wellbeing does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Table 6: Regression ANOVA on Prediction of Psychological Wellbeing to Emotional Intelligence of Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	188.081	1	188.081	25.185	.000 ^b	Ho Rejected
	Residual	5586.027	384	7.468			
	Total	5774.108	385				

a. Dependent Variable: Emotional intelligence of students

b. Predictors: (Constant), Psychological wellbeing

Results in Table 6 reveals that F-value = 25.185, p-value = 0.000^b and degrees of freedom (df) = 1 and 384. Since $F_{(1, 384)} = 25.185$ and p-value (0.000) < 0.05, the null hypothesis that "psychological wellbeing does not significantly predict emotional intelligence of students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area" was therefore rejected. It was therefore concluded that psychological wellbeing significantly predicts emotional intelligence of students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. This result is an indication that psychological wellbeing is a factor that enhances emotional intelligence of students.

Discussion of Findings

Results for research question 1 as shown in Table 1 revealed that home environment predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area to a high extent. The test of its corresponding null hypothesis 1 as presented in Table 4 indicated that home environment significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. This result could be because home environment is the first point of learning and socialization environment for every individual from the day of birth. It could also be attributed to the fact that at home, the parents helps the child develop his/ her thinking capacity and acquires the values of the family as well as shape his/ her personality. The result of this study is in agreement with Naik and Shukla (2018) who investigated the impact of home environment on social and emotional intelligence of adolescents students and reported that there is a significant impact of home environment on interactional effect of social and emotional intelligence of both boys and girls student of higher secondary schools. This show how significant the home environment can positively impact on the development of a child including his/ her emotional intelligence. However, contrary to the result of this study, Singh and Sagar (2019) in their study on emotional intelligence and home environment of senior secondary students found no significant interaction effect between home environment and gender on emotional intelligence of senior secondary students.

Table 2 which shows the results for research question 2 indicated that locus of control predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area to a moderate extent. However, from the test of null hypothesis 2 as presented in Table 5, it was found that locus of control significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. This result could be because, while some individuals tend to exhibit internal locus of control by believing that they have control over events in their lives, others may display external locus of control by not believing that they have control over events that happens in their life. In agreement with the finding of this study, Shah (2017) investigated emotional intelligence among adolescents in relation to their test anxiety and academic stress and found a significant difference among gender in relation to emotional intelligence and test anxiety. Similarly, in their study on emotional intelligence and social maturity in young male and female, Dudhatra and Jogsan (2017) revealed that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and social maturity in young males and females.

From the results presented in Table 3 for research question 3, it was concluded that psychological wellbeing predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area to a high extent. Furthermore, it was found from the test of its null hypothesis 3 as shown in Table 6 that psychological wellbeing significantly predicts emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. The reason for this finding could be due to the fact that psychological wellbeing encompasses the overall effectiveness of a person including his /her emotional functioning. This result corroborated Mehmood and Gulzar (2014) who examined the connection of emotional intelligence with adolescent's psychological wellbeing (depression and self-esteem) and revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and self-esteem of adolescent students. Similarly, Ruiz-Aranda, Extremera and Pineda-Galán (2014) investigated emotional intelligence, life satisfaction and subjective happiness in female student health professionals and found that participants with higher emotional intelligence recorded less perceived stress and higher levels of life satisfaction and happiness. This shows that psychological wellbeing which covers life satisfaction and happiness is very much important for achievement of high emotional intelligence among students.

CONCLUSION

This study which investigated determinants of emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area revealed that home environment, locus of control and psychological wellbeing significantly predict emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. Hence, it was concluded that emotional

intelligence of students is strongly determined by the students' home environment, locus of control and psychological wellbeing.

Implications for Counselling

The following are some of the implications for counselling:

1. There is need for the school counsellors to regularly engage the students on issues that will enhance their emotional intelligence.
2. Family counselling should be given proper considerations by parents and counselors in order to ensure that the children's emotions and psychological wellbeing are being maintained and balanced.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should make the home environment to be conducive as to enhance the emotional intelligence of the students.
2. Students should develop internal locus of control in order to believe in themselves, as well as improve their emotional intelligence for better performance in school.
3. Psychological wellbeing of students should be a priority in the training and upbringing of students in order to enhance their emotional intelligence.

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